

Flow-powered Low cut-in speed Oscillating Subsea System for marine current energy harvesting (FLOSS)

Saurabh Agrawal, Caroline Lowcher, Andre Mazzoleni

The US marine energy resources from rivers, tidal, and ocean currents constitute an estimated yearly potential of 368 TWh/yr. Traditional marine hydrokinetic energy (MHK) technologies are designed to capture this energy and include horizontal and vertical axis turbines. For Gulf Stream applications, innovative torque-canceling coaxial turbines are being developed, intended for deployment far from shore and at large depths. Platform-tethered kite-based systems are also being developed for applications in low-velocity currents by inducing kite flow speeds to be significantly higher than the current. While these technologies show promise for converting MHK energy, they face inherent challenges and limitations. Most traditional turbine systems have a minimum required cut in speed of 1m/s (many marine currents have flow speeds less than 1m/s), with maximum power being generated at flow speeds of 2.5m/s or above, making them not suited to extract energy in low flows. Additionally, turbine-based systems generate power based on high-speed rotational components. This can have a direct impact on marine life and the environment either through direct collisions or indirectly by generating noise from rotating parts or scouring of the sedimentation after the turbine is deployed in shallower waters. These systems are susceptible to biofouling that commonly occurs on the lift-generating surfaces and negatively impacts the system's performance.

To address these limitations, the work done proposes a novel fluid kinetic energy conversion device, FLOSS, that has the ability to generate energy in a wide range of currents with almost no cut-in speed requirement. Operate in shallow water depth regions with a low marine environment impact and require a lower control effort.

FLOSS uses a drag-based approach to generate energy. It incorporates two variable-sized drag bodies that can change size either mechanically via linear actuators or pneumatically through inflation, a cable of a semi-rigid nature that traverses through a central housing coupled to a transmission system and generator. The central housing acts as the primary mooring point for the system. In free stream flow, two bodies of equal size experience equal amounts of drag since the drag force is proportional to surface area. Here, both bodies remain stationary. When the size or area of the drag bodies is changed, the first body area is increased and the second is reduced simultaneously. The higher drag force acting on the larger body causes it to move in the direction of flow, with the smaller second body moving in the opposite direction. By alternating the sizes of the two bodies in the flow, a reciprocating motion is achieved. This operation, resembling

“flossing”, causes the generator shafts to rotate, thereby generating power. With virtually no cut-in speed limitations and the ability to operate in any flow regime, with minimal to no design change needed to optimize for every flow regime, FLOSS offers tremendous potential as a unique, scalable, low environmental impact current energy harvesting device.

Fig.1: Visualization of FLOSS

Fig.2: Working principle